

PROTOCOL FOR SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

This document consists in a protocol to be followed for the conduction of a systematic literature review. To establish this protocol, we followed the guidelines for conducting secondary studies proposed by Kitchenham and Charters [1] and Wohlin [2].

OBJECTIVE

To characterize the current state of research on fault tolerance for Smart City Applications.

QUESTION FORMULATION

- **RQ1:** Which fault tolerance techniques have been used in Smart City Applications?
- **RQ2:** Which types of faults, errors, and failures are involved in Smart City Applications, and which of them have been handled in terms of fault tolerance techniques?
- **RQ3:** How mature is research on fault tolerance for Smart City Applications?

SEARCH STRING COMPOSITION

Group 1 of Keywords and Synonyms: “smart city”; “smart cities”; “smart solution”; “smart solutions”;

Group 2 of Keywords and Synonyms: "fault-tolerance" OR "fault tolerance" OR "fault-tolerant" OR "fault tolerant" OR "dependability" OR "dependable" OR "error recovery" OR "error handling" OR "reliable" OR "resilient";

Group 3 of Keywords and Synonyms: (“fault type” OR “error type” OR “failure type” OR “fault characterisation” OR “fault characterization” OR “fault classification” OR “error characterisation” OR “error characterization” OR “error classification” OR “failure characterisation” OR “failure characterization” OR “failure classification”);

String 1: Group 1 AND (Group 2)

String 2: Group 1 AND (Group 3)

SEARCH ENGINE SELECTION

We selected the Scopus search engine since it covers traditional repositories of scientific literature in the field of Computer Science such as IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital library,

ScienceDirect and SpringerLink. Additionally, we used the Google Scholar search engine to apply the snowballing techniques.

List of Selected Sources:

- Elsevier Scopus: <https://www.scopus.com/>
- Google Scholar (for snowballing): <https://scholar.google.com/>

SELECTION OF STUDIES

Inclusion (I) Criteria:

- I1: The study defines or applies fault tolerance techniques for Smart City Applications (RQ1, RQ3)
- I2: The study defines catalogues, classifications or taxonomies of faults, errors or failures for Smart City Applications (RQ2, RQ3);
- I3: The study is a primary study;

A study is selected if it passes (I1 OR I2) AND I3.

Exclusion (E) Criteria:

- E2: The study is not written in English.
- E3: The study is not peer-reviewed.

Studies that fall into at least one of the above categories are not selected.

Study Selection Based on Results from the Automatic Search:

- **Step 1 - Duplicate study filtering:** The automatic search sometimes retrieves the same study more than once. This step filters and removes duplicate studies. Note that even using only Scopus to retrieve studies, the search engine may find the same title in, for example, two different databases. In this case, the StArt [3] tool – which supports SLRs – tags the duplicates and provides the user with the option to exclude them. In this SLR, the StArt option to exclude all duplicates is used. Some duplicates must be identified by hand because of minor differences in the citations.
- **Step 2 - Initial selection of studies:** Read the title, abstract and keywords of each study, and apply the inclusion and exclusion criteria to decide whether to read the full paper. The selected studies are thereafter called pre-selected studies.
- **Step 3 - Final selection:** read each study in full. While reading, once again apply the inclusion and exclusion criteria to decide if the study should be included in the final set of studies. In case of indecision, start a discussion with other researchers until a decision about including the study in the final set is made.
- **Identifying overlappings:** after analyzing the studies, identify possible overlaps among them. This happens when a study is extended, updated, or improved by their authors, or when a paper published in a scientific event is superseded by a journal publication. When an overlap is detected, use the more comprehensive, usually the latest published, study version.

Application of snowballing:

Backward and Forward Snowballing are applied in the final set of studies. Backward snowballing comprises the analysis of each selected study. Forward snowballing consists of analyzing studies that cited the selected studies. For forward snowballing, use the Google Scholar search engine <<https://scholar.google.com/>>. For this SLR, snowballing is performed at one level of depth (that is, one iteration) for both forward and backward searches. Inclusion and exclusion criteria are applied initially at the title and abstract of retrieved studies, and subsequently to the whole body of pre-selected studies.

EXTRACTION OF DATA AND STUDY CLASSIFICATION

Data Extraction Fields (supports subsequent study classification):

1. A summary of the study
2. Publication year
3. Type of the research
4. Type of contribution
5. Application domains and sub-domains of Smart Cities
6. Type of architecture
7. Fault tolerance technique
8. Description of faults, errors, and failures, when available in the study

Description of the Study Classification Schema:

Selected studies are classified according to the following categories of information:

- **Type of Research:** it follows the classification devised by Wieringa et al. [4], which includes six categories: validation research, evaluation research, solution proposal, philosophical paper, opinion paper, and experience paper. It should be taken into account the decision table proposed by Petersen et al. [5], which is aimed at supporting researchers in the process of categorizing the type of research according to Wieringa et al.'s classification. Details of each type are as follows:
 - A study is classified as **validation research** when it proposes a solution by following a research setup such as experiments, simulation, prototyping, mathematical analysis, mathematical proof of properties, *etc*, but was neither implemented in practice nor in a controlled experiment.
 - In **evaluation research**, an empirical evaluation was undertaken in a real scenario (e.g. an industrial case study, or a controlled experiment with practitioners). If the experiment used data from real scenarios, the study also was classified as evaluation research.

- A study is classified as a *solution proposal* if it presents a novel solution, but an empirical evaluation was not performed.
 - A ***philosophical paper*** presents a conceptual framework.
 - ***Opinion papers*** contain the author's opinion about what is good or bad about something, or present guidelines of how one should do something
 - ***Experience papers*** report on the author's personal experience.
- **Type of Contribution:** Petersen et al. [5] proposed guidelines for conducting systematic mapping studies in software engineering by classifying studies based on their type of contribution. The intent is to determine the type of intervention being studied and investigated, which could be a process, a method, a model, a tool, or a metric. In this SLR, the classification of the type of contribution is performed by using the ISO/IEC/IEEE International Standard - Systems and Software Engineering – Vocabulary (ISO/IEC/IEEE, 2017). The standard provides a common vocabulary applicable to systems and software engineering.
 - **Application Domains and Sub-domains:** this classification identifies which application type has been addressed by the studies in terms of city space that the application functionality serves. It uses the classification established by Sánchez-Corcuera et al. [6], which includes the following domains and subdomains:
 - ***Government-related domain:*** Focused on improving government efficiency by enabling citizens and other relevant organizations to monitor public services. The subdomains of this group are: City Monitoring, e-Government, Emergency Response, Public Safety, Public Service, and Transparent Government.
 - ***Citizen-related domain:*** Focused on the citizen. These services allow citizens to travel and move efficiently, by accessing real-time information from public services. The subdomains of this group are: Smart Traffic, Public Transport, Tourism Entertainment, Healthcare, Education Consumption, and Social Cohesion.
 - ***Business-related domain:*** Focused on improving logistics and supply chain platforms, expanding trade partners and customers in the city, facilitating entrepreneurship and investment, upgrading the business activity in a city (such as production, commerce, agriculture and consulting) and encouraging the innovation. Its subdomains are: Advertisement, Agriculture, Entrepreneurship, Enterprise Management, Logistics, and Transaction.
 - ***Environment-related domain:*** Focused on delivering more sustainable, economic, and secure energy and water supplies by using more green or renewable energy, recycling and treating waste efficiently and safely, and reducing and preventing pollution in the city. The related subdomains are: Housing, Smart Grids, Water Management, Renewable Energy, Waste Management, Pollution Control, Building, Community, and Public Space

- **Type of Architecture:** this classification identifies the type of system architecture the solution (*i.e.* the contribution) was proposed for regarding Edge, Cloud, and Fog Computing technologies, when such information is available in the selected studies.
- **Fault Tolerance Technique:** this classification regards the characteristics of the fault tolerance techniques investigated in the context of Smart City Applications. It is a central element for the answer to RQ1. This classification relies solely on the set of selected studies.
- **Types of Faults, Errors and Failures:** this classification concerns the characteristics of the faults, errors and failures that are described in the selected studies. This classification is a key element to answer RQ2 and relies solely on the set of selected studies.

SYNTHESIS OF RESULTS

Extracted data from selected studies must be analyzed to:

- (1) Characterize fault tolerance techniques
- (2) Characterize faults, errors, and failures;

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- [3] E. Hernandez, A. Zamboni, S. Fabbri, and A. Di Thommazo, 2012. Using GQM and TAM to Evaluate StArt - a Tool that Supports Systematic Review. CLEI Electronic Journal 15, 3 - 3.
- [4] R. Wieringa, N. Maiden, N. Mead, and C. Rolland, 2006. Requirements Engineering Paper Classification and Evaluation Criteria: a Proposal and a Discussion. Requirements Engineering 11, 102-107.
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[6] R. Sánchez-Corcuera, A. Nuñez-Marcos, J. Sesma-Solance, A. Bilbao-Jayo, R. Mulero, U. Zulaika, G. Azkune, and A. Almeida, 2019. Smart cities survey: Technologies, application domains and challenges for the cities of the future. *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks* 15.